

ESTIMATION OF SERUM INTERLEUKIN 15 IN WOMEN WITH ECTOPIC PREGNANCY AND MISSED ABORTION IN COMPARISON WITH NORMAL PREGNANCY IN TIKRIT TEACHING HOSPITAL

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Abstract: This study aims to assess the role of IL-15 serum measurement at 6-8 weeks in identifying failed pregnancies, ectopic or missed abortions, and healthy intrauterine pregnancies. A case control study was conducted at Tikrit Teaching Hospital, involving 90 patients (Ectopic pregnancy (30 patient) and missed abortion (30 patient), and control (30 pregnant women without complication). Data was collected through questionnaires, ultrasound examinations, and serum samples. The study aims to improve the diagnostic accuracy of ectopic pregnancy.

The study found that the mean age of the missed abortion group was 26.78 ± 5.30 , while the EP group had a mean age of 28.7 ± 6.2 . The mean interleukin-15 levels were significantly higher in the EP group (65.5 ± 14.42) pg/ml compared to the missed abortion group (33.21 ± 8.0) pg/ml, and control group (14.4 ± 4.12) pg/ml.

The receiver operating characteristic curve for diagnosing failed pregnancy and missed abortion determined the cut of value of 22.4 pg/ml as best area 99.8%, and 99.6% respectively. while for ectopic pregnancy was 29.55 pg/ml was the best area under curve 100%. The specificity was higher for the failed pregnancy and missed abortion was 96.7%, and 96.6%, while in ectopic pregnancy when we chose the cutoff point 29.55 was 100%. The precision was 98.36, 96.77, and 100% for the failed pregnancy missed abortion and ectopic pregnancy respectively.

High interleukin -15 levels were associated with failed pregnancies, so these patients need to be closely follow interleukin -15 in diagnosis of ectopic and missed abortion.

Keywords: ectopic pregnancy, failed pregnancy, missed abortion, IL-15.

INTRODUCTION

An abortion is the loss of a pregnancy before 20 weeks of gestation. Missed abortion (MA), commonly referred to as silent miscarriage, typically happens when an embryo or fetus dies, but the body continues to secrete hormones despite the pregnancy loss, this relatively common complication affects about 15% of all clinically diagnosed pregnancies [1]. In Iraq the prevalence of missed abortion 28% [2].

Atypical intrauterine environment, immunological dysfunction, endocrine problems, excessive smoking, severe systemic infections, dietary deficiencies, environmental toxins, and trauma are some of the additional risk factors for MA [3,4].

Ectopic pregnancy (EP) is the implantation of an embryo outside the uterine cavity with the most location of EP is in the fallopian tube, known as tubal EP. tubal EP is one of the most causes of maternal morbidity and mortality in the first trimester [5,6]. The incidence of TEP is approximately 1–2% of all pregnancies in the US and Europe. In developing countries, the incident rate of tubal EP is higher and the mortality rate is about 10% [5,7]. Unless a normal early intrauterine pregnancy (IUP) is visible by ultrasound, diagnosis can be a challenge [8]. When these patients present with pain and/or vaginal bleeding, the differential diagnosis between IUP and missed abortion or ectopic pregnancy is very difficult [9].

The fear of intervening in the case of a desired pregnancy without certainty of diagnosis must be carefully weighed against the risk of misdiagnosing a missed abortion instead of an EP, due to the inherent danger to the mothers suffering an EP of tubal rupture and intraperitoneal hemorrhage. Pregnancy is a natural example of an immune reaction occurring for a determined time period in the organism which opposes the rules of graft rejection [10].

The semi or allogeneic fetal components in a normal pregnancy growing in the privileged site of uterus, not only escape maternal immune attack but also are supported by the maternal immune system [10]. Given the present lack of a clinically useful test for the accurate diagnosis of EP, there is a need to select out those immunological factors measured in the maternal serum, that are involved in the potentially disturbed maternal immune system's answer to the semi-allogeneic conceptus in failed pregnancy cases and display the most promise to differentiate abortion and EP as potential biomarkers [11]. During implantation and early pregnancy, the immunological processes that take place within the uterus are to a great extent modulated by pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines and their altered expression in the maternal serum may play a role in early pregnancy failure [12]. Successful pregnancy is considered a T helper 1 (Th1)- Th2 cooperation phenomenon, with a predominantly Th2 type lymphocyte response and specific cytokine production [13]. Th2 responses favor a cytokine milieu that promotes the induction of autoantibodies and several studies have attempted to link pregnancy failures and/or neonatal diseases with the presence of specific autoantibodies [14].

The IL-15 cytokine is expressed by human placental tissue culture, its serum levels correlate with the duration of the pregnancy and it is maximally expressed during the implantation period in the deciduas [14,15]. Notably, recurrent abortion cases are characterized by an upregulation of IL-15 expression in trophoblasts [16], suggesting that IL-15 can be a marker for pregnancy failure. At 6–8 weeks gestational age the clinical differential diagnosis of a failed pregnancy is difficult due to uncertain dates of the last menstrual period or irregular cycles. We therefore set out to assess whether IL-15 serum measurement at 6–8 weeks could contribute to the differential diagnosis between failed pregnancies, whether EP or missed abortions, and healthy intrauterine pregnancies (IUP).

This study aimed to assess whether IL-15 serum measurement at 6-8 weeks could contribute to the differential diagnosis between failed pregnancies, whether ectopic or missed abortions, and healthy intrauterine pregnancies.

MATERIAL

A case control study done in Tikrit Teaching Hospital from 1st October 2023 to the 1st Jan 2024. Convenient sample of 90 patients selected from department of Obstetrics and gynecology in Tikrit Teaching Hospital. Ectopic pregnancy (30 patient) and missed abortion (30 patient), and control (30 pregnant women without complication). Data collected through: Questionnaire regarding the sociodemographic, obstetrical, gynecological history and history of the current pregnancy, abdominal pain, vaginal bleeding. Ultrasound

examination, and Serum samples will be collected at the initial visit before treatment. If the diagnosis is to make on the first visit, the patient was admitted and followed up until a diagnosis of a viable intrauterine pregnancy or missed abortion or ectopic pregnancy was confirmed. interleukin -15 ELISA measurements: interleukin -15 measured using ELISA.

IL-15 ELISA Measurements: IL-15 measured using ELISA. 5 cc blood will be collected then processed by centrifuge (1,000 g for 15 minutes), and the supernatants were stored at -800 C until assayed. Serum concentrations of IL-15 were determined by quantitative Sunlong Medical™ Human IL-15 ELISA Kit (Catalog Number: EL0218Hu) which is used for the quantitative determination of human Interleukin 15 (IL-15) concentrations in cell culture supernates, serum and plasma.

Statistical methods: Standard statistical procedures will be used to analyze the data. Data will be described as mean \pm standard deviation and percentages. ANOVA and chi-square test were used to calculate P values. The receiver operating curve ROC was used to identify the cutoff point, sensitivity, specificity and precision was calculated. SPSS version 23 and Microsoft Excel software were used for data analysis. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations:

The study was proposed and approved by the scientific committee of the College of the Medicine/University of Tikrit. All participating individuals was gave informed consent for the study, and written approval taken after explaining the aim of the study thoroughly and clearly with ensuring the anonymity and confidentiality of responses.

RESULTS

The mean age group among EP was 28.7 ± 6.2 , among missed abortion group was 26.78 ± 5.30 , and normal pregnancy group was 26.90 ± 4.6 , this relation was statistically not significant. History of abortion found among 10(33.33%) of EP group, 20(66.67%) of missed abortion group, and 9(30%) of the control group, this relation was statistically significant p value < 0.05 . History of infertility found among 11(36.67%) of EP group, 4(13.33%) of missed abortion group, and 2(6.67%) of the control group, this relation was statistically significant p value < 0.05 , as shown in (table 1)

The mean IL-15 was higher among EP group (65.5 ± 14.42) pg/ml, was higher than missed abortion group (33.21 ± 8.0) pg/ml, and the two group were higher than the control group (14.4 ± 4.12) pg/ml, this relation was statistically significant using analysis of variance (ANOVA) p value < 0.001 , as shown in (Table 2).

The post hoc test show that there were significant difference between EP group and missed abortion group , the EP group was higher by 32.37 ± 2.53 pg/ml, (p value < 0.05). The IL-15 was lower than the EP group by (-51.12 ± 2.53) pg/ml, and from the missed abortion by (-18.81 ± 2.53) pg/ml, these relations were statically significant as shown in (Table 3).

Receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) for diagnosis of failed pregnancy (EP and missed abortion) found that for the cutoff point 22.4 pg/ml was the best area under curve 99.8 %, as shown in (Figure 1).

The ROC curve for diagnosis of Ectopic pregnancy found that for the cutoff point 29.55 pg/ml was the best area under curve 100 %, as shown in (Figure 2).

The ROC curve for diagnosis of missed abortion found that for the cutoff point 22.4 pg/ml was the best area under curve 99.6 %, as shown in (Figure 3).

The sensitivity was 100% for all groups regarding the cutoff point 22.4 pg/ml for the failed pregnancy and missed abortion and in ectopic pregnancy for the cutoff point 29.55. The specificity was higher for the failed pregnancy and missed abortion was 96.7%, and 96.6%, while in ectopic pregnancy when we chose the

cutoff point 29.55 was 100%. The precision was 98.36, 96.77, and 100% for the failed pregnancy missed abortion and ectopic pregnancy respectively, as shown in (Table 4).

DISCUSSION

The mean age among missed abortion group was 26.78 ± 5.30 , which is lower than 35 years old. The mean age group among EP was 28.7 ± 6.2 . In previous studies, it was believed that advanced age was a high risk factor for missed abortion, which might result from the decline of ovarian function and corpus luteum function as age accrued [17,18]. As controversial regarding age existed in previous studies, our result showing that age of women with missed abortion was lower than 35 years. This goes with Jiang WZ et al [19] 2022 found that 50.8% of the patient aged < 35 years. The lower age might be related to factors like increasing pressure, unhealthy living habits and environmental pollution resulting from social developing [20]. The mean age group among EP was 28.7 ± 6.2 . This goes with Yahya SA. [21] In Iraq 2020 found that the 59% of females were at age group 21–30 years old. This also consistent with Attri S [22] who found the mean age of the studied patients was (26.1 ± 4.29) years, ranging from 18 to 40 years, with the majority (56.9%) falling within the 20-24 age range.

In this research the result indicates a significantly the history of infertility found higher among EP 11(36.67%), than missed abortion group 4(13.33%), and control group 2(6.67%). This goes with Muzaffar U et al [23] found that the 22.6% of ectopic pregnancies had history of primary infertility compared to 2.9% of controls.

The mean IL-15 was significantly higher among PE group (65.5 ± 14.42) pg/ml, was higher than missed abortion group (33.21 ± 8.0) pg/ml, and the two group were higher than the control group (14.4 ± 4.12) pg/ml. This goes with Saldanha CL et al [51] in 2023 who found that the mean serum IL-15 in ectopic pregnancies was 58.91 ± 7.94 pg/ml. The mean serum IL-15 in missed pregnancies was 58.47 ± 10.94 pg/ml while as it was 47.90 ± 9.66 pg/ml in normal pregnancies, Saldanha CL et al reported higher levels of IL-15 among the 3 study groups and found a significant difference between failed pregnancy and normal pregnancy but no difference between ectopic pregnancy and missed abortion. This was differ from our results in which we found that the ectopic group was significantly higher than the missed abortion group, and both groups differ significantly from the control group. [23]

Daponte A et al [24] 2013 found that the IL-15 concentrations were significantly higher in 60 pregnancy failures (median 19.86, IQ range 16.04–26.97 pg/mL) compared to women with a viable IUP (median 15.06, IQ range 12.74–21.41 pg/mL) and this was highly significant. IL-15 concentrations were significantly higher in women with EP (median 24.9 pg/mL) compared to patients with IUP (15.06 pg/mL).

The inflammatory cytokines such as interferon gamma, TNF, IL-15, IL-12, IL-10, IL-6, and soluble IL-2 receptor have been reported to increase in the serum or plasma of patients with a missed abortion. In studies, it has been reported that defective placentation can cause a missed abortion, which can cause a maternal systemic inflammatory response. These findings suggest that inflammation plays an important role in the development of a missed abortion. [25] IL-15 expression is upregulated in placental tissue of disturbed first trimester pregnancy and the trophoblast cells were detected as main source of IL-15. Though IL-15 is abundantly expressed in non pregnant uterus and in uteroplacental unit during pregnancy [26] its unrestrained expression is associated with spontaneous and recurrent miscarriages [15].

The trophoblast invasion in ectopic pregnancy is different from normal pregnancies and this may explain differences related to IL-15 tissue expression and circulating levels of this cytokine [27]. Trophoblast infiltrating the tube or the peripheral natural killer (NK) cells can be the source of the increased levels of IL-15 in EPs compared to IUPs, but this needs to be explored further. It is in accordance to our finding of increased IL-15 levels in EP which due to its protective effect might explain the surviving of trophoblasts while penetrating the tubal wall. [5,28]

The sensitivity was 100% for all groups regarding the cutoff point 22.4 pg/ml for the failed pregnancy and missed abortion and in ectopic pregnancy for the cutoff point 29.55. The specificity was higher for the failed pregnancy and missed abortion was 96.7%, and 96.6%, while in ectopic pregnancy when we chose the cutoff point 29.55 was 100%. The precision was 98.36, 96.77, and 100% for the failed pregnancy missed abortion and ectopic pregnancy respectively. This goes with Daponte A et al [24] 2013 found that found that IL-15 showed high diagnostic accuracy for the discrimination of a viable IUP from an EP with an area under the curve (AUC) 0.818, and at the threshold of 16.1 pg/mL, had a sensitivity of 92% and a specificity of 68%, and a clinically important negative predictive value (NPV) of 0.999 for diagnosing a normal from an EP. According to this, if the IL-15 concentration is less than 16 pg/mL it is highly unlikely that the pregnant woman suffers from an EP.

Saldanha CL et al [29] in 2023 found that, AUC for IL-15 was 0.787 for comparing missed vs normal pregnancy. At the IL-15 reading of 51.29 pg/ml, the sensitivity was 80% and the test expects 30.8% false positivity rate in distinguishing missed abortion from normal pregnancy. The AUC for ectopic vs normal pregnancy was 0.827. At the IL-15 reading of 49.47 pg/ml, the sensitivity was 92% and the test expects 37% false positivity rate in distinguishing ectopic pregnancy from normal pregnancy. The AUC for failed vs normal pregnancy was 0.810 (p=0.000) (figure 5). At the IL-15 reading of 49.47 pg/ml, the sensitivity was 86% and the test expects 34.6% false positivity rate in distinguishing failed pregnancy (EP, MP) from normal pregnancy. However the AUC was 0.53 when they compared ectopic pregnancy with missed abortion.

CONCLUSION

High IL-15 levels were associated with failed pregnancies, so these patients need to be closely followed. Health education of the medical professionals about the importance of IL-15 in diagnosis of ectopic and missed abortion.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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TABLES

Table 1: General Characteristics of the Study Groups

	EP		missed		normal		P value
	No.	%	Nob.	%	No.	%	
Age	28.7 ± 6.2		26.78 ± 5.30		26.90 ± 4.6		>0.05
GA	10.02 ± 2		8.56 ± 1.5		9.1 ± 1.7		>0.05
parity							
0	11	36.7	8	26.7	13	43.3	>0.05
1–3	13	43.3	10	33.3	11	36.7	
≥3	6	20.0	12	40.0	6	20.0	
history of previous EP	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	
history of abortion	10	33.33	20	66.67	9	30.00	< 0.05
History of operation	13	43.33	6	20.00	7	23.33	>0.05
History of infertility	11	36.67	4	13.33	2	6.67	< 0.05
Use of contraception	5	16.67	2	6.67	4	13.33	>0.05

Table 2: The Mean IL-15 Level among Study Groups.

Study Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	ANOVA p value
Ectopic pregnancy	30	65.50	14.42	< 0.001
Missed abortion	30	33.21	8.00	
Normal pregnancy	30	14.40	4.12	
Total	90	37.70	23.34	

Table 3: Post Hoc Tests of the Mean of IL-15 of Different Study Groups

(I) Study group	(J) Study group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ectopic pregnancy	Missed abortion	32.37*	2.53	0.00	27.3	37.3
Normal pregnancy	Ectopic pregnancy	-51.12*	2.53	0.00	-56.1	-46.1
Normal pregnancy	Missed abortion	-18.81*	2.53	0.00	-23.8	-13.8

*significant relation P value < 0.05

Table 4: Sensitivity, Specificity and Precision of IL-15 in Diagnosis Of Ectopic Missed And Failed Pregnancies

Study Groups	value of the IL-15	sensitivity	False positive	specificity	Precision	AUC*
Failed Pregnancy	22.4	100	3.3	96.7	98.36	99.8
Missed Abortion	22.4	100	3.3	96.7	96.77	99.6
Ectopic Pregnancy	29.55	100	0	100	100	100

*area under curve

Abbreviations:

EP: Ectopic pregnancy, IUP: Intrauterine Pregnancies, MA: Missed abortion,

Th1:T helper 1

FIGURE

Figure 1: The ROC Curve for the IL-15 in Diagnosis of Failed Pregnancy

Figure 2: The ROC Curve for the IL-15 in Diagnosis of Ectopic Pregnancy

Figure 3: The ROC Curve for the IL-15 in Diagnosis of Missed Abortion